

NDAC/LO/154
July 11, 1995

HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, XXII
by S. Söderhjelm, Lund Observatory

This is a short status report for the (almost) final DS solutions produced from May-95 Case History Files.

1. Standard solutions

After the new covariance-calibrations reported in NDAC/LO/153, I started the full-scale runs of STDDBL and SEEKDBL. For 'known' doubles with good previous solutions (agreement FAST/NDAC or NDAC/Torino), these previous solutions were used as start elements, but in most other cases the standard 'grid-searches' were performed (for suspected 'new' doubles out to 5 arcsec separation). This takes a lot of computing-time, and with the experiments reported below (and without exclusive use of the computer...), these runs took almost 2 months to complete. Although (as reported in NDAC/LO/153) the 'band'-structure in a sep/dm-diagram for the new doubles is diminished, it is still very conspicuous, and there are also many 'problem cases' where neither a double nor a single-star solution seems to fit the data. Some of these systems have been solved using a priori parameters from FAST or (older) NDAC solutions, but several hundred more should eventually have a solution. For lack of time, I stopped 'mass-production' of solutions on July 7:th, and the present report is based on the data collected up till then.

With the 'quality-index' defined in NDAC/LO/153, one can make the crude statistics in Table 1a. With many different runs and different a priori inputs, the difference between 'known' and 'unknown' systems is not very strict, but I have tried to be consistent with the definitions leading to the comparable Table 1b, in principle calling a system 'unknown' if the solution was started without any a priori parameters. This means that several systems have gone from 'unknown' to 'known', but the overall number of 'poor' ($i_q=0$ or 1) solutions has also increased.

Table 1a. The number of solutions in the different quality-classes, separated according to the a priori knowledge about the system. The numbers in parentheses are the percentages of systems with 'variable components'.

	$I_q = 0$	$I_q = 1$	$I_q = 2$	$I_q = 3$
known a prio	669(10)	777(21)	1676(18)	6880(6)
no a prio data	2344(17)	2215(27)	2173(21)	1568(9)

Table 1b. Corresponding figures for the December -94 preliminary solutions.

	$I_q = 0$	$I_q = 1$	$I_q = 2$	$I_q = 3$
known a prio	464(4)	580(4)	1449(3)	6376(2)
no a prio data	2184(7)	2101(13)	2451(19)	2004(6)

These statistics can be changed a lot by redefining the rather ad hoc quality-index, but they illustrate well the general problem with a lot of poor and/or variable solutions. The 'band'-problem for the new systems is clearly related to the flagging for variability, as can be seen from Fig 1.

Fig. 1. The 'high-dm' part of the 'new' solutions, with the components deemed 'non-variable'(left) or 'variable' (right).

A 'variable'-solution so far excludes a number of observations for the astrometry solution, using them only to derive the photometry, and this obviously makes it easier to obtain grid-step errors and preferred separations even at magnitude-differences below 3.5. (There are few variables with separations smaller than some 0.5 arcsec, because it is then more difficult to solve unambiguously for the individual magnitudes). See further Section 3.

2. Typical uncertainties

As shown in NDAC/LO/153, the solution mean errors can be reliably calibrated at the 10 %-level, and one may plot the sigmas to give a general impression about the accuracies in the parameter determinations. Fig 2 shows the expected rise in the astrometric and photometric relative errors ($=\sigma(\rho)$ and $\sigma(\Delta m)$) with the magnitude-difference. (It is interesting to note the very close quantitative agreement with the 1989 prediction in Fig 13.6 in ESA SP-1111). Fig 3 gives $\sigma(\rho)$ as a function of magnitude while Fig 4 shows similarly the rise of the 'absolute' errors (exemplified by $\sigma(\pi)$) with magnitude. Fig 5 shows finally that the parallax error is almost independent of the separation or the magnitude-difference. For a majority of objects, the errors are satisfyingly small, with the large increases at the faint end due to inescapable photon noise.

Fig. 2. $\sigma(\rho)$ (left) and $\sigma(\Delta m)$ (right) as a function of Δm , for systems with primary magnitude brighter than $H_p=8.5$.

Fig. 3. Astrometric relative error ($\sigma(\rho)$) as a function of the primary magnitude, for systems with $\Delta m < 1$.

Fig. 4. Parallax error as a function of the primary magnitude.

Fig. 5. Parallax error as a function of the separation (left) or the magnitude-difference (right), for systems with primary magnitude brighter than $H_p=8.5$.

The sigmas plotted here are *internally* consistent within 10%, but the FAST/NDAC comparisons hint at a much larger (up to maybe a factor 2) *external* error. The same conclusion may come from comparisons with ground-based speckle data, but further studies are needed.

3. Program experiments for the variable doubles

In the 1994 STDDBL/SEEKDBL programs, there is an 'incomplete' solution for individual component photometry, using a fixed astrometric solution derived by excluding observations far from the photometric median. I have now tried to augment this with a natural iteration loop where a new astrometric solution is derived using the individual photometry data, which are then rederived with the new (fixed) astrometry and so on. Unfortunately, the convergence of this sequence has often been found to be slow and/or erratic, and only for the 'easy' cases one may be sure about the results. In particular, for non-variables (by some criterion), the astrometric and photometric data are close to the 'standard' values. The decreased number of d.o.f. (with totally 'free' individual photometry one uses $5 \times n_{\text{fov}}$ observations to derive $2 \times n_{\text{fov}}$ photometric and 10 astrometric parameters) makes the astrometric sigmas appreciably higher, however, and the standard 'fixed magnitudes' solution is clearly preferable.

For many variables, the new solution does converge, but for many others it does not, and in the July 7 database with solutions, only the 'old' solutions are given. Out of a total of 18302 doubles, as many as 2529 are flagged as variable, and to get more reliable solutions for all of these, more experiments are urgently needed.

4. Other problems

The photometric calibrations used in the May CHF:s lacks a final 'aging-correction'. Probably, each CHF can be rather easily corrected, and then the DS solutions should be rerun (with 'known' parameters, this will only take a few days).

Then there are the multiple stars, which are so far solved only as doubles. A surprising number do get a solution in this way, but in principle it is of course not satisfactory to neglect known information about further components. The total number of objects concerned is less than 1000, and the more numerous variables therefore have a higher priority. In practice, I think it is unlikely that NDAC will produce a large number of reliable multiple star solutions within the present 1995 time-scale for the reductions.

5. Conclusions

1. Some 11000 'good' ($i_q=2$ or 3), non-variable DS solutions are presently available in NDAC, together with 7000 'poor' and/or variable ones.
2. For the reliable solutions, the principles for the merging with FAST data have to be agreed on. This necessitates comparisons in close to the final DMSA format, which have so far not been attempted. Quantitative comparisons with ground-based data are also needed to assess the real quality of the solutions.
3. Only when the merging for the 'easy' systems is well in hand, the decisions about the 'difficult' ones (with different solutions or solutions from only one consortium) can be taken.
4. For the systems with variable components, and ideally also for the multiple stars, improved solution methods may give more reliable solutions, but no success can be guaranteed. The existing NDAC solutions are mostly still useable.